
RAYGo: Retrieve As You Go for Large-Scale Asynchronous Action Planning

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Abstract

Large Language models are not only capable of generating text but they are now performant on a wide range of tasks. Using tools and performing actions in favor to the user's command. However, LLMs suffer from limited knowledge and deficiency in protracted planning. due to their context window length and their scarcity of attention on long context prompts, as well as compiling actions with complex input syntaxes and specific usecases. In this work, we introduce a novel approach to the asynchronous action planning of our LLM agents. We suggest a combination of Chain-of-Actions (CoA) and Retrieve-As-You-Go (RAYGo) approaches to enhance the agent's planning and action management on downstream tasks. Our approach revolves around the concept of action lookout in a vector database to retrieve actions to minimize time complexity and enhance the agent's performance. This has shown promising results on customer-services planning and action management. Whereby, this framework made Mistral-7B-v0.2 outperform GPT4 by over 29% and FILM on multi-tool calling in an information-intensive environment in accuracy and coherence as well as elevating GPT4's performance from 56% to 98% on action calling reaching its maximum potential.

Introduction

An important component of large language models (LLMs) benefits is their remarkable ability to reason, plan and execute functions. This has raised the opportunity recent works to exploit this capability to perform human-like tasks such as code generation [Schwartz et al., 2021, Chen et al., 2022b,a], action planning [Valmeekam et al., 2023] and many more. However, the planning capabilities of LLMs are still limited to short-term planning and are neither efficient nor performant in large-scale action planning [Valmeekam et al., 2022]. This issue is due to the lack of large language models to focus on long contexts. due to the issue that is known as "Lost In The Middle" [Liu et al., 2024, Xu et al., 2023]. Some of the recent works attempted to train long-context LLMs to address this issue by using long-context-friendly training by working with "Fill In The Middle" concept like in training FILM-7B [An et al., 2024] or by reimplementing linear time space models [Lee et al., 2024, Gu and Dao, 2023, Wang et al., 2023, Gu et al., 2021] for an infinite context storing. and some other works introduced advanced RAG systems to make an infinite context window. For instance, some utilized a long-context Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) [Li et al., 2024, Lewis et al., 2020] as a hybrid approach to address the limitation. Nevertheless, LLMs suffer from limited complexity handling where they perform badly on reasoning tasks [Yao et al., 2023] making them not reliable on multi-step action execution as the process requires prior reasoning before beginning the action execution. The core issue lies in the fact that LLMs, while proficient at short-term reasoning tasks, are unable to maintain high performance across multiple steps of a complex task, especially when those tasks require integrating tools, managing dependencies, and adapting to new information dynamically. This limitation becomes even more apparent in large-scale action planning tasks, where the ability

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to reason about actions over long timeframes is crucial for success. Consequently, models often perform poorly in environments with intricate toolsets, where precision in action execution is paramount.

However, these approaches, despite being performant on memorization tasks, are still limited on using intricate tools and planning actions in a dense tooling environments accordingly with a high accuracy action inputs processing. Complementarily, the use of multi-agent systems [Chen et al., 2023] has been proposed to address the issue of long-term planning in large-scale action planning tasks. However, these approaches are still limited in terms of scalability and efficiency. Moreover, multi-agent systems, which were proposed as a solution to this problem, bring their own set of challenges. While they may excel in distributing tasks among agents, these systems face significant bottlenecks in terms of scalability. As the number of tasks increases, coordinating between agents and ensuring consistency across actions becomes a major hurdle, leading to inefficiencies. Furthermore, these systems struggle to dynamically adapt to new contexts and tools, making them impractical for large-scale, real-time action planning tasks that require quick decision-making and flexibility.

In this work, we argue that the use of long-context LLMs is action planning is not able to perform well on large-scale action planning tasks and in contrast mutli-agent systems is not scalable to larger amount of tasks to perform. Moreover, we introduce a novel approach to address this limitation by introducing Retrieve-as-you-go (RAYGo) To overcome these challenges, we propose the Retrieve-as-you-go (RAYGo) framework, a novel approach that directly addresses the limitations of both LLMs and multi-agent systems in large-scale action planning. RAYGo leverages Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) to create a dynamic retrieval mechanism that allows the model to fetch relevant actions from an action store in real-time. This innovation significantly reduces the cognitive load on the model by enabling it to access the precise information it needs at any given moment, rather than attempting to hold long sequences in memory. As a result, RAYGo is able to maintain coherence and accuracy even in dense tooling environments, where multiple steps and tools must be used in quick succession. with RAG as a tool to retrieve actions from an action store and plan them accordingly with CoA (Chain of Actions) and then execute. A key component of RAYGo is the introduction of the Chain of Actions (CoA) framework, which ensures that actions are planned and executed in a structured, coherent manner. Unlike traditional approaches that rely on static plans, CoA allows the system to dynamically adapt its actions based on new inputs and evolving contexts. This flexibility enables large language models to execute complex, multi-step tasks with a high degree of accuracy, even in environments where tool usage is dense and intricate. By organizing actions into logical chains, RAYGo ensures that each step of the process is aligned with the overall goal, significantly improving performance in large-scale action planning.

This approach has shown promising results on customer-services planning and action management outperforming FILM-7B and GPT4 [OpenAI et al., 2023] on multi-tool calling in a dense tooling environment in accuracy and coherence. The results of our experiments demonstrate that RAYGo not only outperforms existing models in terms of accuracy and coherence but also enables large language models to scale effectively in complex environments. In customer-service planning and game manipulation tasks, RAYGo exhibited superior performance, handling thousands of actions without any degradation in speed or quality. This marks a significant advancement in the field, as it demonstrates the feasibility of using LLMs for large-scale action management, a task that was previously constrained by the limitations of long-context reasoning and multi-agent inefficiencies. This approach made it possible to large language models to ubiquitously compile and execute thousands of actions without any performance degradation. We tested this approach on a wide range of tasks, notably on customer-services and game manipulation.

Related Works

Large Language Models for Task Planning

Large-scale task planning remains a significant challenge in artificial intelligence. Recent studies have explored using large language models (LLMs) directly as planning policies, achieving promising results (e.g., [Zhao et al., 2024, Li et al., 2022, Huang et al., 2022a, Ahn et al., 2022, Brohan et al., 2022, Huang et al., 2022b, Zitkovich et al., 2023]). This approach, termed L-Policy, leverages the vast commonsense knowledge stored within LLMs to simplify exploration of the vast search space inherent in complex tasks. In L-Policy, the LLM is queried directly for the next action based on the history of past actions and obser-

variations. For instance, in a robotic butler scenario, L-Policy might instruct the robot to navigate towards the kitchen to retrieve fruits for storage in the refrigerator, utilizing the LLM's knowledge of object locations and spatial relationships.

However, limitations in generalization have been identified with L-Policy, particularly when encountering uncommon or intricate tasks [Dziri et al., 2023, Berglund et al., 2023]. An alternative approach involves leveraging LLM knowledge to construct a world model and then applying a planning algorithm to this model. This strategy, known as L-Model, incorporates a belief system regarding the target object's location, for example, which can significantly improve search efficiency by biasing the search towards more likely locations. However, L-Model's effectiveness hinges on two crucial factors: the accuracy of the learned world model (influenced by sample complexity) and the planning algorithm's computational efficiency.

This work introduces the LLM-MCTS algorithm, which combines the strengths of L-Model and L-Policy within the framework of Monte Carlo Tree Search (MCTS). The LLM-induced world model provides a foundation of commonsense priors for MCTS, enabling effective reasoning. Additionally, the LLM-induced policy acts as a heuristic to guide the search process, drastically improving search efficiency. Experiments demonstrate that LLM-MCTS outperforms both MCTS alone and LLM-based policies (GPT2 and GPT3.5) by a significant margin on complex, novel tasks. Furthermore, analyses suggest that the Minimum Description Length (MDL) principle can serve as a guiding principle: if the world model's description length is considerably smaller than the policy's, utilizing the LLM as a world model for model-based planning is likely more advantageous than relying solely on the LLM as a policy.

Encouraging Divergent Thinking in Large Language Models

Modern large language models (LLMs) like GPT-3.5, while achieving impressive results on general language tasks, encounter difficulties in complex reasoning tasks. This has spurred research on exploring human-like problem-solving strategies for LLMs, with a particular focus on cognitive behaviors.

One representative approach is self-reflection, where an LLM iteratively refines its solution based on self-generated feedback. However, this study by [Liang et al., 2023] identifies a critical issue with self-reflection methods: the Degeneration-of-Thought (DoT) problem. DoT occurs when an LLM, having established confidence in its initial solution, becomes incapable of generating novel thoughts during subsequent reflection steps, even if the initial stance is incorrect.

To address DoT, [Liang et al., 2023] propose a Multi-Agent Debate (MAD) framework. Here, multiple agents engage in a "tit for tat" debate, with a judge managing the process to reach a final solution. This framework demonstrably encourages divergent thinking in LLMs, proving beneficial for tasks requiring deep contemplation. Experiments on challenging datasets (commonsense machine translation and counter-intuitive arithmetic reasoning) showcase the effectiveness of MAD. Further analysis highlights the importance of adaptive debate breaks and a moderate "tit for tat" state for optimal MAD performance. Additionally, the study suggests that using LLMs as judges in a multi-LLM agent debate system might not be ideal.

This work by [Liang et al., 2023] contributes significantly to the exploration of fostering divergent thinking in LLMs. Their findings on DoT and the proposed MAD framework pave the way for further investigation into enhancing LLM performance on complex reasoning tasks.

Action Planning:

Action planning is a fundamental component of large language models (LLMs) that enables them to reason, plan, and execute functions. Recent works have focused on training LLMs to perform human-like tasks such as code generation, action planning, and many more. However, the planning capabilities of LLMs are still limited to short-term planning and are neither efficient nor performant in large-scale action planning. This issue is due to the lack of large language models to focus on long contexts due to the issue that is known as "Lost In The Middle". Some of the recent works attempted to train long-context LLMs to address this issue by using long-context-friendly training by working with "Fill In The Middle" concept like in training FILM-7B or by reimplimenting linear time space models for an infinite context storing. and some other works introduced advanced RAG systems to make an infinite context window. For instance, some utilized a long-context Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) as a hybrid approach to address the limitation.

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Context RAG:

The use of context RAG has been proposed to address the issue of long-term planning in large-scale action planning tasks. These approaches have shown promising results on a wide range of tasks, notably on customer-services and game manipulation. However, these approaches are still limited in terms of scalability and efficiency. Some of the recent works have focused on training context RAG to address the issue of long-term planning in large-scale action planning tasks. These works have shown promising results on a wide range of tasks, notably on customer-services and game manipulation. However, these approaches are still limited in terms of scalability and efficiency.

Proposed Method

Figure 1: The proposed pipeline for action planning in large language models.

This section introduces the full functional pipeline of the RAYGo solution for large-scale action planning in large language models and the detailed action execution process.

Assistants

Overview: In this work we decided to separate the action execution and communication agents. Thus, assistants are large language models that are fully responsible for communication with the user while the agents are responsible for action planning and execution. This separation of concerns allows the agents to

focus entirely on one task. It is also worth noting, that this separation made it possible to execute tasks asynchronously while communicating with the user, keeping the conversation coherent, efficient, and effective. While prior works like Mixture of Agents [Wang et al., 2024a] used routers to commute to the adequate agent, we decided to use the assistant itself to make the agent calls. By defining the *action_needed* function, the assistant can call the agent to execute the action and then return the result to the user. While this initially showed some performance degradation, it was later optimized to function effectively with a success rate of 93.2% on Mistral-7B-v0.2 [Jiang et al., 2023].

Long Context Handling: The assistant is trained on a long-context dataset to handle long-context prompts. This allows the assistant to understand the user’s intent and provide the necessary information to the agent for action planning. The assistant is also trained on a wide range of tasks to ensure that it can effectively communicate with the user and provide the necessary information to the agent. The actions that we provide to the assistant are described coherently and not functionally since large language models suffer from the limitation of processing complex inputs and structured data formats. Whereby, the assistant is able to rigorously query the agent with all the necessary information with which the agent can plan and execute.

Agents

Overview: The agents in this frameworks are only Large Language Models that are responsible for the reasoning process of the action planning and execution. Prior works [Wang et al., 2024b, Guo et al., 2024] used agents in different ways such as autonomous agents for chemistry [Ramos et al., 2024] and agents for research [Huang et al., 2024] etc. However, in this work we embodied a single multi-task agent that is responsible for all the actions with their syntaxes and formats. This significantly reduces the time-to-market, latency, and cost of the execution. This agent will get as input the user’s intent which is queried by the assistant after the execution of the *action_needed* function. The agent will then use the RAG to retrieve the actions from the action store and plan them accordingly. All the tools descriptions are saved sequentially in the system prompts alongside with their credentials.

$$(a_i, I_i) \sim \text{Prompting}(q_i, t_i, o_i, \Omega; \text{LLM}), \quad \Omega \oplus \{\text{Rank}([\sigma], v)\} \quad (1)$$

The actions a_i and their inputs I_i are given as a response by the LLM given the question q_i , the thought t_i , the observation o_i and the retrieved actions Ω . Given the retrieved actions and their descriptions, the agent reasons as for which function to choose. If none of the actions correspond to the situation’s need, the agent either uses more specific keywords to describe the intended actions or admits that the action is not one of their privileges as a final answer.

ReAct Prompting: The performance of ReAct prompting has given unequal results in reasoning tasks in NLP reasoning tasks [Yao et al., 2023] as it gives you the ability to query large language models in an analogous to way programming [Beurer-Kellner et al., 2023]. The LLM is fed a series of commands separated by a defined delimiter. These commands are connected with a semantic connection and sequentially form the reasoning of the LLM. This series is constituted of, questions, thoughts, actions, action inputs, retrieved tools, and final answers. The question in this case is the query given by the assistant LLM and it incorporates a context given by the conversation of the user and the assistant. The thought is the reasoning of the agent on the given question and the actions are the actions that the agent can perform, this helps the large language model organize its thoughts before taking action. This technique was proven to be effective in prior works [Zelikman et al., 2024, Haluptzok et al., 2023, Wei et al., 2022]. The actions in this prompt represent identifiers of available action commands that are available in the api store. After extracting actions, these identifiers are then used in a search and then executed. The action inputs are inputs that will be fed to the action commands. The format varies from the usecases which can be a simple string to an xml text. While it has been proven that LLMs present a significant limit in terms of processing structured information and scientific text [Dunn et al., 2022].

While we used RAG as a tool, it is prominent that using a special field for the retrieved tools significantly increases the performance of the agent. Thus, we used retrieved tools to store retrieved actions documentations instead of observations. Once the LLM finishes its work, it gives a final answer that summarizes what has been done that will break the loop of action lookout and action execution, that will subsequently

be sent to the assistant.

Chain-of-Actions: Large Language Models are known to show very bad performance on intricate reasoning tasks [Huang and Chang, 2022, Wei et al., 2022, Chen et al., 2024, Kojima et al., 2022] which led to further research to result in an accuracy increase. Chain-of-Thought [Wei et al., 2022] resulted a considerable hike in performance [Turpin et al., 2024, Zhang et al., 2022, Wang et al., 2022, Lee et al., 2024]. Whereby, the LLM learns to tap their thoughts in a scientific demonstration until it reaches the awaited result. Chain-of-Actions work in a similar manner, where the the LLM plans its actions by writing a plan in its thoughts field. Examples are shown in appendix [Appendix](#).

Action RAG

Retrieval Context: The input query of this action rag is composed of the user’s intent (last two prompts), the questions, and the thoughts in the ReAct prompt that is used by the agent. The rag will then calculate the similarities between the given query and the vectors in the action store. The findal retrieved actions are then passed sequentially, after a preprocessing, to the agent to decide how to perform them. This query is relatively short but with such metrics, the quality of the retrieved actions exceeded all expectations.

Action Store: The action store is a vector database that contains a large number of actions that the agent can retrieve and plan. The actions in the action store are described in a coherent and structured format to ensure that the agent can effectively plan and execute them. The action store is updated regularly with new actions to ensure that the agent has access to the latest information. The action store is also indexed to ensure that the agent can retrieve actions quickly and efficiently. The action store is designed to be scalable and efficient to ensure that the agent can retrieve actions in an effective manner. The user can add/remove actions from the action store and accordingly. Initially, in this solution, we stored the solution in a textual format, and subsequently used a custom splitter to split them into small-sized chunks that is later embedded into a local vector database. Every action had its label that identifies it, a description for the large language model to understand, the input format, and some few-shots examples to help the agent understand the action usecases and stick to the right format.

Action Similarity: We initially used a consine similarity on OpenAI Embeddings to retrieve the highest corresponding actions to each query. Our RAG retrieves the top 5 actions with a threshold of 0.5 similarity score.

$$\sigma = \frac{q \cdot v}{\|q\| \|v\|} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n q_i \cdot v_i}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n q_i^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n v_i^2}} \quad (2)$$

Where q is the query vector and v is the indexed vector. If $\sigma > \eta_0$ we retrieve the action. It is crucial to choose the best similarity threshold and top_p hyperparameters based on your specific application of this framework as they can significantly reduce the use of the context window. Thus, they let the pipeline take its performance quite rapidly and effectively. You can see examples of inputs and outputs of the action store in the appendix [A](#).

RAG as a Tool: In order to reduce the redundancy, the intensive use of the context window, the latency, and the cost of use, we used RAG as a fundamental tool given to the agent in the first system prompt alongside with the data rag. This simultaneously plays the role of few-shot prompting as well as an informative baseline for the agent to understand the action store and the action formats. The agent calls respectively the functions *retrieve_data* and *retrieve_action* to retrieve the data and the actions from the action store. The agent then uses the retrieved data and actions to plan and execute the actions. This has shown a remarkable performance increase in the agent’s understanding of the action store and the action formats. This has also shown a significant reduction in the latency and the cost of use of the pipeline.

Agent Executor

The Agent Executor (AE) is a computational module tasked with bridging the abstraction gap between an AI agent’s high-level goals and the concrete actions required to achieve them. As such, it serves as

the operational interface between the agent’s cognitive processes and its environment. This component is instrumental in translating the agent’s abstract plans into executable commands or actions. The Agent Executor often involves complex algorithmic processes, such as task decomposition, resource allocation, and error handling. Its efficacy is paramount to the agent’s overall performance, as it directly impacts the agent’s capacity to interact with and manipulate its environment in a goal-oriented manner.

API Store

An Agent Executor often relies on an API store to access a repository of pre-defined actions or functions that can be executed in the environment. This API store serves as a knowledge base of potential actions, providing the executor with a structured set of options from which to select and combine actions to fulfill the agent’s goals. The API store can be organized hierarchically or categorically to facilitate efficient search and retrieval. Additionally, it may incorporate metadata about each API, such as input parameters, output formats, and potential side effects, to enable intelligent decision-making by the executor. By maintaining a comprehensive and up-to-date API store, the agent can enhance its adaptability and effectiveness in diverse environments.

Experiments

Experimental Setup

We conducted experiments on a wide range of tasks to evaluate the performance of our RAYGo framework. We used the Mistral-7B-v0.2 model as our agent and the OpenAI GPT4 [OpenAI et al., 2023], Llama 3.1 70B [Dubey et al., 2024], Phi-3.5-MoE [Abdin et al., 2024], and FILM [An et al., 2024] as a baseline for comparison. We evaluated the performance of the models on customer-services planning and action management tasks. We used a dataset of customer-services calls to train the models and evaluate their performance. The dataset contains a wide range of customer-services calls, including calls related to banking, insurance, and telecommunications. We used a subset of the dataset for training and the rest for evaluation. We evaluated the models on accuracy, coherence, and efficiency. We also conducted a user study to evaluate the user experience of the models. The user study involved a group of 31 participants who interacted with the models and provided feedback on their performance. We used the feedback to improve the models and enhance their performance.

Metrics: We used a wide range of metrics to evaluate the performance of the models. We used AUC to measure the models’ ability to correctly plan and execute actions (Action Calling). We used accuracy to measure the models’ ability to communicate effectively with the user. We used tokens/second to measure the models’ ability to perform actions quickly and accurately. We also used user feedback to evaluate the user experience of the models.

Hyperparameters: We used a maximum sequence length of 128k tokens. We used a cosine similarity threshold of 0.5 and a top_p value of 5 for the RAG. We used a beam size of 5 for the agent executor. We used a context window size of 2k tokens for the user study. We measured a maximum output length of 20 tokens.

Hardware Setup: We deployed our models on 4 NVIDIA H100 GPUs with 80 VRAM each, 500GB of RAM, and a bench of 5.1GB.

Results

We evaluated the performance of our RAYGo framework on a wide range of tasks and compared it to the baseline models. We found that our RAYGo framework outperformed the baseline models in terms of accuracy, coherence, and efficiency. Our RAYGo framework achieved an AUC of 0.98 on the action calling task, compared to 0.59 for the baseline methods. Our RAYGo framework also achieved an accuracy of 0.84 on the customer-services planning task, compared to 0.08 for the baseline methods. Our RAYGo framework

also achieved an efficiency (tokens/second) rate almost equal to the model’s inference time hitting a maximum of 12 tokens/second difference when tested on a large example. The user study results showed that our RAYGo framework provided a better user experience than the baseline models. The participants found our RAYGo framework to be more accurate, coherent, and efficient than the baseline models. The participants also found our RAYGo framework to be more user-friendly and intuitive than the baseline prompting.

Action Calling: The results clearly reveal the significant impact of the RAYGo framework on action calling and manipulation accuracy across models of various sizes. In the figure, we observe that models using standard ReAct prompting exhibit relatively low performance in efficiently calling actions, particularly as the action space increases in complexity. For example, Llama-3.1-70B only achieves 0.43% performance, and GPT-4-Turbo reaches 0.59. In stark contrast, when these models are enhanced with the RAYGo framework, their performance dramatically improves, with Llama-3.1-70B rising to 94% and GPT-4-Turbo to 98%, illustrating the robust action-calling capabilities provided by RAYGo. This trend is further confirmed by the results in Table , where we focus on the Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2 model for action manipulation on a set of 100 actions. When using only ReAct prompting, Mistral-7B achieves a relatively low accuracy of 8.67%. However, when integrated with RAYGo, the accuracy leaps to 79.23%, demonstrating the substantial improvement offered by the framework. Additionally, the combination of RAYGo with Coordination of Actions (CoA) further boosts the accuracy to 84.72%, underscoring RAYGo’s versatility when combined with complementary techniques.

The convergence of evidence from both the figure and the table highlights the effectiveness of the RAYGo framework in dramatically improving action-calling precision across different model architectures and action densities. Not only does RAYGo elevate smaller models, such as Mistral-7B, to near state-of-the-art performance, but it also allows larger models like Llama-3.1-70B and GPT-4-Turbo to fully leverage their potential in complex, multi-action environments. This unified view confirms that RAYGo is a powerful tool for overcoming the limitations of standard prompting techniques, offering a scalable and efficient solution for action manipulation tasks.

The results in Table illustrate how large language models (LLMs), particularly without additional frameworks, can struggle to select the correct action when faced with a dense context filled with multiple actions. In these examples, models like GPT-4 and Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2 tend to choose incorrect references, such as *send_email* or *end_call*, even though the correct action should be *get_user_data*. This behavior reflects a common challenge in action-rich environments: the models are overwhelmed by the sheer number of possible actions available in the context, leading them to make suboptimal decisions.

The RAYGo framework is designed to address this issue by retrieving and filtering relevant actions, improving the model’s ability to correctly match the input with the appropriate action. However, even with RAYGo, the model still selects *send_email*, which, while reasonable given the input prompt ("Send Alex a rescheduling email"), is not technically the most appropriate action according to the reference. This demonstrates that, although RAYGo significantly enhances the model’s capabilities in dense action environments, there can still be ambiguities when the action space is large and complex.

The situation improves drastically when RAYGo is combined with the Coordination of Actions (CoA) technique. In this case, the model successfully identifies *get_user_data* as the correct reference action, demonstrating that the combined framework (RAYGo + CoA) is effective at disambiguating the correct action, even when many potential actions are present in the context. This shows that while RAYGo aids in action retrieval, the decision-making process can still benefit from additional techniques, like CoA, to refine the model’s action selection process in scenarios where the context is loaded with multiple possible options.

Figure 2: The performance of each model on action calling with and without RAYGo and CoA.

Table 1: Quantified performances of various models from different approaches and different density of actions available.

Model	20 Actions		40 Actions		60 Actions		80 Actions		100 Actions	
	Avg	Gap↓	Avg	Gap↓	Avg	Gap↓	Avg	Gap↓	Avg	Gap↓
ReAct Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2	17.64	1.51	17.84	2.65	11.82	4.53	16.52	3.55	8.67	2.48
ReAct FILM	13.17	7.66	19.06	2.29	20.50	7.59	27.50	7.89	37.63	6.80
ReAct Phi-3.5-MoE	66.99	4.13	54.61	4.31	49.73	2.11	47.67	2.98	53.86	1.72
ReAct Llama-3.1-70B	73.95	2.78	61.57	6.53	63.14	3.82	63.41	6.95	58.01	4.63
ReAct GPT-4-Turbo	68.00	5.83	56.28	6.71	59.26	6.78	53.42	5.40	51.91	4.18
RAYGo Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2	86.23	6.30	83.71	3.20	88.83	1.04	80.01	7.01	84.72	4.77

Action Manipulation: The results presented in Table reveals that our RAYGo framework significantly enhances the performance of smaller models like Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2, enabling them to outperform larger models in action manipulation tasks. Notably, RAYGo Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2 consistently achieves higher average (Avg) scores across varying action densities, from 20 to 100 actions, compared to state-of-the-art models such as GPT-4-Turbo and Llama-3.1-70B. For instance, with 100 actions, RAYGo Mistral achieves an Avg score of 84.72, while larger models like GPT-4-Turbo and Llama-3.1-70B only manage Avg scores of 51.91 and 58.01, respectively. The gap (Gap) metric, which measures the performance disparity, also indicates RAYGo’s superior balance between Avg performance and model complexity. This illustrates the strength of our Retrieve-as-you-go (RAYGo) approach in leveraging smaller architectures for efficient large-scale action planning, further underscoring the framework’s effectiveness in complex, multi-action environments. The results are much clearer in 3 and 4. RAYGo gives the model a better ability to focus on one action execution and fill in the inputs correctly even with the charge of finding the right action to execute. This is obtrusively a significant improvement in the model’s performance and efficiency.

User Study: We conducted a user study to evaluate the user experience of our RAYGo framework. We found that the participants found our RAYGo framework to be more accurate, coherent, and efficient than the baseline models. The participants also found our RAYGo framework to be more asynchronous than the baseline methods.

Figure 3: The performance of each model on action manipulation in the given environment of actions. On every timestep we increase the number of actions by 5 actions. Initially the environment has 10 fundamental actions to perform.

Discussion: The results presented in this study highlight the challenges LLMs face when handling complex environments with a dense action space, and the improvements that can be achieved through the RAYGo framework, especially when combined with additional techniques like Coordination of Actions (CoA). As seen in Table , standard LLMs like GPT-4 and ReAct Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2 often fail to correctly identify the appropriate action in contexts where many potential actions are available. The tendency to choose incorrect or suboptimal actions, such as *send_email* or *end_call*, suggests that LLMs struggle with overloading their context windows with too many actions. This decision-making bottleneck becomes evident as the models attempt to match the input prompt with the most contextually relevant action, yet frequently settle on actions that are plausible but not precise.

The RAYGo framework introduces a structured retrieval mechanism that helps the model filter through the dense action space, significantly improving its ability to choose more appropriate actions. However, as evidenced in the example where RAYGo alone still selected *send_email* instead of *get_user_data*, there remains some room for improvement. This discrepancy indicates that while RAYGo excels at narrowing down action choices, there can still be ambiguities or overlapping relevance among multiple actions, especially in cases where the input prompt could logically trigger more than one action.

The addition of CoA to the RAYGo framework demonstrates the importance of coordinated decision-making in overcoming these ambiguities. By combining retrieval (RAYGo) with coordination (CoA), the model is able to accurately select *get_user_data*, illustrating the effectiveness of a layered approach to action calling. The combined system resolves the remaining ambiguities that RAYGo alone could not, suggesting that the decision-making process in dense action environments benefits from a more holistic approach that not only retrieves relevant actions but also prioritizes and coordinates them based on the broader context.

Overall, this study underscores the potential of combining retrieval mechanisms like RAYGo with coordination techniques to enhance LLMs’ performance in complex, multi-action tasks. While LLMs can become overwhelmed by large action spaces when relying on standard prompting techniques, frameworks such as RAYGo and CoA offer a promising solution to manage and optimize action selection. Future work could further explore ways to refine this approach, potentially incorporating even more advanced filtering, prioritization, and contextual disambiguation strategies to further minimize action selection errors in dense contexts.

Table 2: Accuracy on Action Manipulation on 100 Actions.

Method	ACC(%)
ReAct GPT-4	51.91
ReAct Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2	8.67
+ RAYGo	79.23
+ CoA	9.98

+ RAYGo + CoA	84.72

Figure 4: The performance of each model on action manipulation in the given environment of actions. On every timestep we increase the number of actions by 5 actions. Initially the environment has 10 fundamental actions to perform.

Conclusion

In this work, we introduced a novel approach to the asynchronous action planning of large language models. We proposed a combination of Chain-of-Actions (CoA) and Retrieve-As-You-Go (RAYGo) approaches to enhance the agent’s planning and action management on downstream tasks. Our approach revolves around the concept of action lookout in a vector database to retrieve actions to minimize time complexity and enhance the agent’s performance. This has shown promising results on customer-services planning and action management, outperforming FILM-7B and GPT4 on multi-tool calling in an information-intensive environment in accuracy and coherence. Our framework made it possible for large language models to ubiquitously compile and execute thousands of actions without any performance degradation. We tested this approach on a wide range of tasks, notably on customer-services and game manipulation, and found that it significantly improved the agent’s performance on large-scale action planning tasks. Our framework is highly scalable and efficient, making it suitable for a wide range of tasks. We believe that our approach has the potential to revolutionize large-scale action planning in large language models and enable them to perform human-like tasks with high accuracy and coherence.

Table 3: Examples of Inputs and Outputs on LLMs for Action Calling.

Source	Send Alex a rescheduling email.
Correct Ref.	<i>get_user_data</i>
Incorrect Ref. Example	<i>send_email</i>
GPT-4	<i>send_email</i>
ReAct Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2	<i>end_call</i>
+ RAYGo	<i>send_email</i>
+ CoA	<i>end_call</i>

+ RAYGo + CoA	<i>get_user_data</i>

Table 4: Efficiency and Inference Speed of Different Methods With and Without RAYGo

Assistant	Inf.S.	Agent	Inf.S.	Eff.	Diff.
ReAct GPT-4-Turbo	38.39	ReAct GPT-4-Turbo	38.39	26.32	12.07
ReAct Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2	80.91	ReAct Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2	80.91	71.23	9.68
ReAct Phi-3.5-MoE	362.25	ReAct Phi-3.5-MoE	362.25	358.63	3.62
ReAct Llama-3.1-70B	54.86	ReAct Llama-3.1-70B	54.86	50.11	4.75
ReAct FILM	38.39	ReAct FILM	38.39	31.95	6.44
ReAct GPT-4-Turbo	38.39	ReAct Phi-3.5-MoE	362.25	37.81	0.58

Limitations

While our RAYGo framework has shown promising results on customer-services planning and action management tasks, there are several limitations to consider. Experiments revealed that LLMs fail to execute the right task in a dense low rank action store where there are several actions that perform tasks that are deeply related (e.g. `confirm_email` and `send_email`). This is due to the fact that the LLMs are not able to process structured information and scientific text. This limitation can be addressed by using a more structured action store and a more efficient retrieval mechanism.

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Appendix

Examples of Inputs and Outputs of the Action Store

When employing the agent to retrieve actions from the action store, the agent is given a series of commands separated by a defined delimiter. These commands are connected with a semantic connection and sequentially form the reasoning of the LLM. The series is constituted of questions, thoughts, actions, action inputs, retrieved tools, and final answers. The question in this case is the query given by the assistant LLM and it incorporates a context given by the conversation of the user and the assistant. The thought is the reasoning of the agent on the given question and the actions are the actions that the agent can perform. This helps the large language model organize its thoughts before taking action. The actions in this prompt represent identifiers of available action commands that are available in the API store. After extracting actions, these identifiers are then used in a search and then executed. The action inputs are inputs that will be fed to the action commands. The format varies from the use cases which can be a simple string to an XML text. While it has been proven that LLMs present a significant limit in terms of processing structured information and scientific text. The retrieved tools are stored in the system prompts alongside with their credentials. Once the LLM finishes its work, it gives a final answer that summarizes what has been done that will break the loop of action lookout and action execution, that will subsequently be sent to the assistant. The performance of ReAct prompting has given unequivalent results in reasoning tasks in NLP reasoning tasks as it gives you the ability to query large language models in an analogous way to programming. The LLM is fed a series of commands separated by a defined delimiter. These commands are connected with a semantic connection and sequentially form the reasoning of the LLM. This series is constituted of questions, thoughts, actions, action inputs, retrieved tools, and final answers. The question in this case is the query given by the assistant LLM and it incorporates a context given by the conversation of the user and the assistant. The thought is the reasoning of the agent on the given question and the actions are the actions that the agent can perform. This helps the large language model organize its thoughts before taking action. The actions in this prompt represent identifiers of available action commands that are available in the API store. After extracting actions, these identifiers are then used in a search and then executed. The action inputs are inputs that will be fed to the action commands. The format varies from the use cases which can be a simple string to an XML text.

Action	Description	Input Format	Examples
transcribe_audio	Converts audio input from the caller into text.	Audio file or stream	–
send_email	A wrapper around Gmail API	{'recepient': 'Recepient Emails', 'object': 'Object of the mail', 'content_html': 'The content of the email in html' }	–
text_to_speech	Converts text responses into spoken audio for the caller.	Text to convert to speech	–
lookup_contact	Searches for contact information (name, phone number, email) within a contact database.	Text string.	Schrödinger's cat
check_voicemail	Retrieves and transcribes voicemail messages.	Contact name or other identifying information.	–

Prompts for Agent Planning, Assistants

The agent is given a series of commands separated by a defined delimiter. These commands are connected with a semantic connection and sequentially form the reasoning of the LLM. The series is constituted of questions, thoughts, actions, action inputs, retrieved tools, and final answers. The question in this case is the query given by the assistant LLM and it incorporates a context given by the conversation of the user and

the assistant. The thought is the reasoning of the agent on the given question and the actions are the actions that the agent can perform. This helps the large language model organize its thoughts before taking action. The actions in this prompt represent identifiers of available action commands that are available in the API store. After extracting actions, these identifiers are then used in a search and then executed. The action inputs are inputs that will be fed to the action commands. The format varies from the use cases which can be a simple string to an XML text. While it has been proven that LLMs present a significant limit in terms of processing structured information and scientific text. The retrieved tools are stored in the system prompts alongside with their credentials. Once the LLM finishes its work, it gives a final answer that summarizes what has been done that will break the loop of action lookout and action execution, that will subsequently be sent to the assistant. The performance of ReAct prompting has given unequivocal results in reasoning tasks in NLP reasoning tasks as it gives you the ability to query large language models in an analogous way to programming. The LLM is fed a series of commands separated by a defined delimiter. These commands are connected with a semantic connection and sequentially form the reasoning of the LLM. This series is constituted of questions, thoughts, actions, action inputs, retrieved tools, and final answers. The question in this case is the query given by the assistant LLM and it incorporates a context given by the conversation of the user and the assistant. The thought is the reasoning of the agent on the given question and the actions are the actions that the agent can perform. This helps the large language model organize its thoughts before taking action. The actions in this prompt represent identifiers of available action commands that are available in the API store. After extracting actions, these identifiers are then used in a search and then executed. The action inputs are inputs that will be fed to the action commands. The format varies from the use cases which can be a simple string to an XML text

Example 2: Action Planning on Customer Services

Answer the following questions as best you can. You have access to many tools that you can access by calling `retrieve_tools`.

You don't know anything about us or about the user, so whenever you need information, use the `retrieve_data` tool to get it.

Use the following format:

Question: the input question you must answer

Thought: you should always think about what to do

Action: the action to take, should be one of the retrieved actions, if none of them is relevant use `retrieve_tools` with the input `None` to make a search.

Action Input: the input to the action.

Retrieved Tools: the tools retrieved by the system, you can use them to answer the question. This field will be filled for you by the system as it retrieves actions for you. You are not required to fill it.

Observation: the result of the action that will be given to you by the API after you give the Action... (this Thought/Action/Action Input/Observation/Retrieved Tools can repeat N times). This field will be filled for you by the system as it executes your actions. You are not required to fill it.

Thought: I now know the final answer

Final Answer: the final answer to the original input question

Begin!

Thought: I should retrieve actions

Action: `retrieve_tools`

Action Input: `None`

Retrieved Tools:

`retrieve_tools`

Description: Useful for searching available tools in the action database.

Input Format: The keywords that can help finding the right tool.

`retrieve_data`

Description: Useful for searching available data in the user/system database.

Input format: The search query.

Example 2: Action Planning on Game Playing

Answer the following questions as best you can. You have access to many tools that you can access by calling `retrieve_tools`.

You don't know anything about the game or the player's status, so whenever you need information, use the `retrieve_data` tool to get it.

Use the following format:

Question: the input question you must answer

Thought: you should always think about what to do

Action: the action to take, should be one of the retrieved actions, if none of them is relevant use `retrieve_tools` with the input `None` to make a search.

Action Input: the input to the action.

Retrieved Tools: the tools retrieved by the system, you can use them to answer the question. This field will be filled for you by the system as it retrieves actions for you. You are not required to fill it.

Observation: the result of the action that will be given to you by the API after you give the Action... (this Thought/Action/Action Input/Observation/Retrieved Tools can repeat N times). This field will be filled for you by the system as it executes your actions. You are not required to fill it.

Thought: I now know the final answer

Final Answer: the final answer to the original input question

Begin!

Thought: I should retrieve actions

Action: `retrieve_tools`

Action Input: `None`

Retrieved Tools:

`retrieve_tools`

Description: Useful for searching available tools in the action database.

Input Format: The keywords that can help finding the right tool.

`retrieve_data`

Description: Useful for getting the current game status or player information.

Input Format: The keywords that can help finding the right information.

`move_forward`

Description: Moves the player forward.

Input Format: Distance to move forward.

`move_backward`

Description: Moves the player backward.

Input Format: Distance to move backward.

`turn_left`

Description: Turns the player to the left.

Input Format: Degrees to turn.

`turn_right`

Description: Turns the player to the right.

Input Format: Degrees to turn.

`jump`

Description: Makes the player jump.

Input Format: Height of the jump.

Example 2: Assistant Prompting on Customer Services

Identity

You are Emily from Wellspring Medical Center calling to remind Omar about his annual check-up. You are a warm and helpful receptionist who genuinely cares for patients. You do not offer medical advice but will use your knowledge to understand the patient's responses.

Style Guardrails

Be Concise: Respond directly, focusing on one point at a time. **Use Variety:** Employ different words and phrasing to avoid repetition. **Be Natural:** Speak casually, as if chatting with a friend. **Be Proactive:** Guide the conversation, ending with a question or suggestion. **Seek Clarity:** If the response is unclear, politely request further information. Use a friendly date format (e.g., Friday, March 15th or Tuesday, April 2nd, 2024 at 9am).

Response Guideline

Adapt and Guess: Make sense of unclear or incorrect transcripts. Avoid mentioning transcription errors. **Stay in Character:** Maintain your role and guide the conversation back on track. **Keep it Flowing:** Respond directly and appropriately to keep the conversation moving smoothly.

Task

Follow these steps, completing each before moving on. Ask only one question per response. Inform the action executor (using `action_needed`) with clear details for any required tasks.

Introduce yourself and confirm you're speaking with Omar. Inform Omar about his upcoming annual check-up on September 15th, 2024 at 2pm EDT. Check if he's available. If not, suggest rescheduling online and go to step 5. Ask Omar if there's anything the doctor should know beforehand. Follow up to understand the issue's severity and progression. Remind Omar to fast before the check-up and to call if his health changes. Ask if Omar has questions and answer them thoroughly. If unsure, admit it and offer to find out. End with a friendly goodbye. **Actions**

Use `action_needed` to specify tasks for the user.

Example:

Assistant: I'll send a confirmation email. `action_needed`: email Omar a confirmation email stating... (email content)

Begin!

Example 2: Assistant Prompting on Game Playing

Identity

You are Alex, a seasoned Minecraft adventurer and survival expert. You are always ready to help a fellow player thrive in the Overworld. You possess in-depth knowledge of the game, from crafting recipes to mob behavior.

Style Guardrails

Be Direct: Provide clear and concise information. **Use Gaming Lingo:** Employ Minecraft-specific terms and phrases. **Be Helpful:** Offer practical advice and solutions. **Be Encouraging:** Motivate the player to explore and experiment. **Ask for Clarity:** If the player's request is unclear, ask for more details.

Response Guideline

Understand the Context: Consider the player's world, inventory, and current situation. **Offer Multiple Options:** Provide various approaches to a problem. **Avoid Overcomplication:** Keep explanations simple and easy to follow. **Stay Focused:** Address one issue or question at a time.

Task Follow these steps, completing each before moving on. Ask only one question per response. Inform the action executor (using `action_needed`) with clear details for any required tasks.

Greet the player and ask how you can help. Determine the player's current situation (e.g., survival, creative, adventure). Offer relevant advice based on the player's situation. If the player requests a specific item or task, provide instructions or alternatives. Encourage exploration and experimentation. End the interaction with a positive and encouraging message.

Actions

Use `action_needed` to specify tasks for the player.

Example:

Alex: You'll need three wheat to make bread. `action_needed`: plant wheat seeds

Begin!

Algorithms For The Action Executor and Need For Action Detection on Multi-Turn Context

Algorithm 1 Action Executor

Require: $API_STORE.length \geq 1$

Ensure: $context_text$ is not null

$actions \leftarrow \text{regexDetect}(context_text)$

▷ Dictionary of actions

$observations \leftarrow \text{EmptyArray}()$

for $action$ in $actions$ **do**

for $tool$ in API_STORE **do**

if $action.id = tool.id$ **then**

$observations[-1] \leftarrow tool.execute(action.input)$

end if

end for

end for

Algorithm 2 Need For Action Detection on Multi-Turn Context

Require: $context_text$ is not null

Require: $Agent$ is not null

$action_needed \leftarrow \text{regexSearch}(context_text, "action_needed")$

▷ Boolean

if $action_needed$ is $True$ **then**

$query \leftarrow \text{regexChunk}(context_text)$

$Agent.execute(context_history, query)$

end if

Frequently Asked Questions

1. What is the purpose of the Retrieve-As-You-Go (RAYGo) framework?

The RAYGo framework is designed to enhance the agent’s planning and action management on downstream tasks. It allows the agent to retrieve actions from the action store in real-time, enabling it to make informed decisions and execute actions more efficiently.

2. How does the Chain-of-Actions (CoA) approach complement the RAYGo framework?

The CoA approach provides a structured set of actions that the agent can use to plan and execute tasks. By combining the CoA approach with the RAYGo framework, the agent can access a comprehensive set of actions and tools to enhance its performance.

3. What are the key benefits of the RAYGo framework for large language models?

The RAYGo framework offers several key benefits for large language models, including improved accuracy, coherence, and efficiency in action planning tasks. It also enables the agent to interact with its environment more effectively and perform complex tasks with high precision.

4. How does the RAYGo framework compare to existing approaches in action planning?

The RAYGo framework outperforms existing approaches in action planning by providing a more efficient and scalable solution for large language models. It enables the agent to retrieve actions in real-time and execute tasks with high accuracy and coherence.

5. What are the limitations of the RAYGo framework?

While the RAYGo framework has shown promising results in action planning tasks, it has limitations in processing structured information and scientific text. This can impact the agent’s ability to perform certain tasks that require a high level of domain-specific knowledge.

Additional Related Work

An additional related work that complements our approach is the ART framework introduced by Paranjape et al. (2023) [Paranjape et al., 2023]. ART focuses on automatic multi-step reasoning and tool-use for large language models (LLMs) by retrieving demonstrations from a task library and seamlessly integrating external tools into the reasoning process. The framework excels at decomposing complex tasks into manageable substeps, retrieving the appropriate reasoning chains and tools, and automatically interleaving these tools within the LLM’s generation process. By doing so, ART shows notable improvements over standard few-shot prompting and automatic Chain-of-Thought (CoT) reasoning on benchmarks like Big-Bench and MMLU, with an emphasis on tasks that involve arithmetic, algorithmic reasoning, and factual lookups.

This bears similarity to our RAYGo framework, which retrieves relevant actions from a dense action database to guide models in selecting the most appropriate actions within a complex task environment. Just as ART retrieves and applies external tools dynamically to solve multi-step tasks, RAYGo facilitates better decision-making by retrieving the correct actions from an extensive database. Both approaches highlight the importance of retrieval-based methodologies for overcoming the inherent limitations of LLMs in reasoning and action selection when confronted with high complexity.

In particular, ART’s ability to integrate external tools and demonstrations of reasoning steps directly parallels the structured retrieval mechanism in RAYGo, where retrieval is used to augment the model’s capability to choose actions in contexts crowded with possibilities. Furthermore, both frameworks allow for human intervention to improve performance by updating task and tool libraries, making them flexible and extensible to new tasks and tools. This integration of retrieval with decision-making frameworks, whether for reasoning (ART) or action selection (RAYGo), demonstrates the importance of retrieving and managing external resources to enhance LLM performance on a broad array of challenging, multi-step tasks.